

Development of Innovative Islamic Web Applications

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Abstract—The rich Islamic resources related to religious text, Islamic sciences, and history are widely available in print and in electronic format online. However, most of these works are only available in Arabic language. In this research, an attempt is made to utilize these resources to create interactive web applications in Arabic, English and other languages. The system utilizes the Pattern Recognition, Knowledge Management, Data Mining, Information Retrieval and Management, Indexing, storage and data-analysis techniques to parse, store, convert and manage the information from authentic Arabic resources. These interactive web Apps provide smart multi-lingual search, tree based search, on-demand information matching and linking. In this paper, we provide details of application architecture, design, implementation and technologies employed. We also presented the summary of web applications already developed. We have also included some screen shots from the corresponding web sites. These web applications provide an Innovative On-line Learning Systems (eLearning and computer based education).

Keywords—Islamic resources, Muslim scholars, hadith, narrators, history, fiqh.

I. INTRODUCTION

THERE are few websites and online resources available today which provide authentic Islamic knowledge in English or any other language except Arabic. There is huge collection of Islamic resources available online in Arabic. In this work, an effort is made to utilize some of these resources to develop innovative and interactive web applications.

The aim of this project is to provide easy to use, readily available and searchable authentic information related well known Islamic resources. It benefits Muslim community in general and students of knowledge in particular. As most of the Muslims are non-Arabs, this is the only source available online or offline today in English, for them to learn about different aspects of religious knowledge including ahadeeth of Prophet (saw) with chain of narrators, Muslim scholars, Islamic history, comparative Fiqh, etc. Non-Arabic speaking Muslims and student of knowledge can greatly benefit from this website without reading through huge volume of books in Arabic. Even for Arab Muslims, these web applications provide Islamic knowledge in an innovative and concise manner.

A. Benefits

- This is believed to be first extensive work in English on Islamic knowledge.
- The huge database of resources (Arabic) containing multi-volume books on Islamic sciences, hadith narrators and scholars are available for easy access.

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- The scholar information is interlinked within these resources, enabling access to original information about a particular scholar/narrator.
- Different variations of name and kunya for a particular narrator/scholar are captured.
- Known family members (parents, siblings, spouses, and children) are also recorded.
- Information like date of birth/death, places of stay, teacher and student list and narrator grade/rank provide useful details about hadeeth narrators.
- Student of hadeeth sciences can greatly benefit in the field of 'ilm al-rijal (knowledge of men/authorities), tabqat al-ruwat (classes of narrators) and al-jarh wa'l-ta'dil (impugment and validation).
- This website/database can also serve as a resource for takhreej al-hadeeth.
- Quick access to all related scholars/narrators info is provided by utilizing time-lines.

B. Features

- It includes all major collections of ahadeeth (in progress).
- Arabic text and English translation are sourced from sunnah.com website.
- Information can be searched in many different ways (including keywords, Arabic text, Narrator name, etc.).
- Search options including Smart search box on top, Advanced search form and search by compilation or narrator.
- Narrators are linked to Muslim Scholar Database for detailed biography.
- Instant snapshot of Narrator's brief bio for each hadith.
- Detailed hadith referencing.
- Translation can be viewed in several languages using Google translate toolbox.
- Interactive Narrators' timeline for each hadith.
- Detailed Statistics based on ahadeeth narrated by a certain narrator.
- Color-coded narrator names based on generation (tabqa)

The rest of this paper is organized as follow. In Section II, we provide some background on Islamic writing with focus on books written on Men (scholars). In Section III, we provide the application design and implementation details in general. We presented summary of the some sites with screen shot in Section IV. The conclusion and future work are provided in Section V.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

One of the first book written on Seerah of Prophet (saw) was dated back to around 150 AH (after Hijri) i.e around 700

CE by Ibn Ishaq [1]. Later specific books were written on scholars, including At-Thiqat [3], al-Tarikh-ul-Kabir [4] and Tabaqat [2]. These are considered original resources as they were compiled in the 3rd century (Hijri). These compilation deals with the narrators of hadith in a general way. In the next few centuries (from 900 CE to 1200 CE), some great books were written on Islamic and general history such as The History of al-Tabari [5]. These resources not only describes the conquests and defeats but give detailed insight on the people living in those times in history including rulers, commander and scholars.

The later scholars wrote books on men of Hadith of particular book or group of books like 'six books'. Ibn Hajar al-'Asqalani [7] and Muhammad ibn Ahmed ibn 'Usman al-Dhabbi [6] are famous authors of such writings. They have written multiple books on hadeeth narrators and scholars including people who claimed to be scholars like lairs in hadith and fabricators. These writings are based on original sources mentioned above and other similar sources. Ibn Hajar al-'Asqalani placed the narrators into twelve ranks. The ranks as named and categorized by Ibn Hajar are widely accepted but not universal. Another great resource is Tahdheeb al-Kamal by al-Mizzi [8] with information broken down into lines, making it compatible with data mining tools available now a days. Recently, many of these books are translated in English and other languages. In our work, we utilized all above work as well as some recent books translated in English such as [9]-[11].

III. APPLICATION DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION DETAILS

A. Offline Processing of Islamic Resources

The first phase was to process and convert needed huge collection of Islamic resources (mostly unstructured raw text files) into a structured database (RDMS). These resources, which are authentic multi-volume books in Arabic of Islamic knowledge and sciences, are available in the E-book format. They were downloaded and converted into several Arabic text files (UTF format). Some computer programs and scripts were written and run on these text files to convert raw information and store into a database (separating text into records). This resource database is also searchable via advanced search option in the web applications. This process is summarized in Fig. 1. In the second phase (Fig. 2), required information from resource database were extracted by running the set of intelligent computer programs using the knowledge management techniques and extract, transform and load methods (ETL). Another set of programs translated/converted the extracted information into English and stored them into the application database utilizing pattern recognition and artificial intelligence techniques. Then information is properly linked and cross-referenced among the different tables using semi-automatic methods where special computer programs were used to manually perform the job.

B. Software Reuse and Agile Development

In today's agile world of software development, applications are usually not created from scratch but already developed

Fig. 1 Phase I - Raw data files to Resource database

Fig. 2 Phase II - Information from Resource DB to Application DB

components and frameworks are employed as the starting point. The software is developed in phases where some parts of the complete system are developed in initial or prototype phase. We utilized all these modern concepts of software development. Several of the components developed for one web application are later utilized by the others. Similarly, the information or database is shared between applications.

C. Application Architecture

A system development methodology refers to the framework that is used to structure, plan, and control the process of developing an information system. Fig. 3 illustrates the generic architecture of the web application.

Fig. 3 Application architecture

Fig. 4 Home page of Muslim Scholars Database website

D. Technology Employed

We have employed existing state-of-the-art technology of web design and development. We use Apache web server on Linux operating system to host our application. MySQL database is utilized to store all related tables for resources and application DB and to perform SQL queries (simple or complex) to search within the DB. We use PHP for dynamic content and on the user interface side we utilize, HTML, CSS, JavaScript and jQuery.

IV. SUMMARY OF WEB APPLICATIONS

There are four separate web applications which are available as of today. Although the framework is available, information has been added gradually and these applications will continue to expand in future.

A. Muslimscholars.info

This is an effort to collect, compile and store (electronically, in one place) authentic information about Muslim scholars since the advent of Islam more than 1400 years ago. The first phase of the project includes the biographical information of the first 4 generations, covering the first 300 years after

the migration of Prophet (saw). This interactive website has been developed to display/search the information in various different ways. The work is in progress since March 2009. Fig. 4 shows the home page of the website with search bar. Some prominent companions and scholars are listed on the right side. Fig. 5 shows a part of a scholar detailed view (<http://muslimscholars.info>).

B. QaalaRasulAllah.com

It is an interactive and innovative web application which provides hadith text (matn), translation (English and other languages) and interactive chain of narrators (isnad) for all major hadith compilation. This huge effort is work in progress and is believed to be first extensive work in English on hadith narrators. The unique feature is that narrators are linked to Muslim Scholars Database (muslimscholars.info) to provide detailed biographies of each narrator. Information can be searched in many different ways (including keywords, Arabic text, Narrator name, etc.) and can be analyzed/accessed/compared using interactive Trees and Timelines. Other features include: Instant snapshot of narrator's brief bio for each hadith, detailed hadith referencing,

زبير بن العوام بن خويلد (رضي الله عنه)

Select Language ▼

Scholar: 7 - Zubayr ibn al-Awwam [Abu 'Abdullah] Comp. (RA) [1st Generation]

Full Name: Zubayr ibn al-'Awwam bin Khuwaylid bin Asad bin 'Abdul-Uzza bin Quasyy bin Kilab b. Murrh

Parents: Awwam ibn Khuwaylid bin Asad bin 'Abdul-Uzza / Safiyya bint 'Abd al-Muttalib

Siblings: al-Saib bin al-'Awwam bin Khuwaylid, Zaynab bint al-'Awwam bin Khuwaylid, Umm Habib bint al-'Awwam bin Khuwaylid, 'Abdur Rahman bin al-'Awwam, 'Ubaidullah bin al-'Awwam, Bujayr bin al-'Awwam bin Khuwaylid

Birth Date/Place: 28 BH/596 CE (Makkah)

Death Date/Place: 36 AH/656 CE (Medinah)[Martyred(Jamal)]

Places of Stay: Makkah/Medinah

Area of Interest: Recitation/Quran, Narrator [ع - صحابة], Fiqh, Commander

Spouse(s): Asma' bint Abi Bakr, Umm Khalid bin Khalid ibn Sa'id, Umm Kulthum bint 'Uqba, al-Rabab bnt Unaif, Zainab bint Bishr, al-Halal bint Qays, Tumadir bint al-Asbagh Kalbia

Children : 'Abdullah ibn al-Zubayr, al-Mundhir bin al-Zubayr, 'Urwa ibn al-Zubayr, 'Asim ibn al-Zubayr, al-Muhajir ibn al-Zubayr, Khadija al-Kubra bint al-Zubayr, Ummul Hasan bint al-Zubayr, 'Aisha bint al-Zubayr, Khalid bin al-Zubayr, 'Amr bin al-Zubayr, Habibah bint al-Zubayr, Sawda bint al-Zubayr, Hind bint al-Zubayr, Zainab ibn al-Zubayr, Mus'ab ibn al-Zubayr, Hamza bin al-Zubayr, Ramla bint al-Zubayr, 'Ubaida bin al-Zubayr, Ja'far bin al-Zubayr, Hafsa bint al-Zubayr, Khadija al-Sughra bint al-Zubayr

Fig. 5 A part of a scholar view from muslimscholars.info

Sahih Bukhari Book: 2, Hadith: 33

Arabic ▶ حَدَّثَنَا سَلِيمَانُ أَبُو الرَّبِيعِ، قَالَ حَدَّثَنَا إِسْمَاعِيلُ بْنُ جَعْفَرٍ، قَالَ حَدَّثَنَا نَافِعُ بْنُ مَالِكِ بْنِ أَبِي عَامِرٍ أَبُو سُهَيْلٍ، عَنْ أَبِيهِ، عَنْ أَبِي هُرَيْرَةَ، عَنِ النَّبِيِّ صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ قَالَ " آيَةُ الْمُنَافِقِ ثَلَاثٌ إِذَا حَدَّثَ كَذَبَ، وَإِذَا وَعَدَ أَخْلَفَ، وَإِذَا أَوْثِمَ خَانَ "

English ■ Narrated Abu Huraira:
The Prophet said, "The signs of a hypocrite are **three**:
1. Whenever he speaks, he tells a lie.
2. Whenever he promises, he always breaks it (his promise).
3. If you trust him, he proves to be dishonest. (If you keep something as a trust with him, he will not return it.)"

Chain(0) ▶ **Sulaiman bin Da'ud al-'Atki al-Zahrani** —→ **Isma'il bin Ja'far bin Abi Kathir** —→ **Nafi' bin Malik bin Abi 'Amir**
—→ **Malik bin Abi 'Amir** —→ **Abu Hurairah**

Sulaiman bin Da'ud al-'Atki al-Zahrani (10)
30137-Sulaiman bin Da'ud al-'Atki al-Zahrani (10)
Abu al-Rabi' [Thiqah]
[~140 AH - 234 AH]
al-Basra, Baghdad
al-Zahrani, al-'Atki, al-Basri, Baghdad, Imam, Hafiz

Isma'il bin Ja'far bin Abi Kathir (8)
20155-Isma'il bin Ja'far bin Abi Kathir (8)
Abu Ishaq [Thiqah]
[>100 AH - 180 AH]
Medina, Baghdad
Ansar, B.Zurayq, Client, Madni

Nafi' bin Malik bin Abi 'Amir (4)
11445-Nafi' bin Malik bin Abi 'Amir (4)
Abu Sahi [Thiqah]
[d. after 140 AH]
al-Asbahi, Ally B.Taym, al-Madni

Malik bin Abi 'Amir (2)
11443-Malik bin Abi 'Amir (2)
Abu Anas, Abu Muhammad [Thiqah]
[d. 74 AH]
Medina
al-Asbahi, Ally B. Taym, al-Madni

Abu Hurairah (0)
13-Abu Hurairah (0)
Abu Hurairah
[12 BH/603 CE - 59 AH/681 CE]
Makkah/Medina/Yemen/Bahrain
Yemeni, Dausi, Client, Late Muslim

Reference: Sahih al-Bukhari 33
In-book reference: Book 2, Hadith 26
English translation: Vol. 1, Book 2, Hadith 33
Source: Sunnah.com

Fig. 6 A detailed hadith view from QaalaRasulAllah.com

translation can be viewed in several languages using Google translate toolbox, interactive narrators' timeline for each hadith, and color-coded narrator names based on his/her generation (tabqa). Fig. 6 shows <http://qaalarasulallah.com/>

C. Fiqhpedia.com

It is an Encyclopedia of Islamic Fiqh/Rulings containing Opinion of 4 Madhaib and other Scholars. It provides evidences from Quran & Sunnah, reasons for disagreements, rulings related of Ibadat and Mumalat, searchable Quran & Hadith Resources, English/Arabic search, Interactive Tree

Lookup and much more. Fig. 7 shows detailed opinion of scholars on a fiqh issue. Quranic and hadith references are highlighted and can be viewed on mouse click. User can select the issues from the side tree (<http://Fiqhpedia.com>).

D. history.muslimscholars.info

This site provides authentic and Interactive timeline of Islamic History. It includes life and stories of Prophets, life and events during Prophet Muhammad (saw), history of rightly guided Caliphs, history of later caliphs (Umayyad, Abbasid, etc.), Islamic history of Spain, Africa, Sub-continent,

The screenshot shows the FiqhPedia.com website interface. On the left is a navigation menu with categories like 'Worship', 'Book of Purification (Tahara)', 'Book of Bathing', etc. The main content area is titled 'Water Mixed with Impurities without a change in its attributes'. It includes the book title 'The Book of Ritual Purification (Tahara)', chapter 'The Kinds of Water Used', and a specific topic/issue: '31 - Water Mixed with Impurities without a change in its attributes -- الماء إذا خالطته نجاسة ولم تغير أحد أوصافه'. Below this is a table of opinions from various scholars, including Imam Malik, Imam Abu Hanifa, and Imam Shafi, with their respective explanations and reconciliations. A 'Disagreement Reasons' section lists two points: '1. The water is pure irrespective of large or small quantities (the majority)' and '2. If it is little, then it becomes impure (ash-Shaff'ee)'. The page also includes 'Evidences' and 'Tags'.

Fig. 7 Opinion of scholars on a Fiqh issue

The screenshot shows the Islamic History website. The main header features the title 'Islamic History' and the subtitle 'Authentic Information about Islamic History'. Below the header are navigation tabs for 'Prophets', 'Rulers', 'Regions', and 'Useful Links'. The main content area is titled 'Brief Biography of Prophet Muhammad (saw) - محمد صلى الله عليه وآله وسلم'. It features a horizontal timeline from 818H to 30AH, with various events marked by blue dots and numbered. The events include: (1) Muhammad's Birth and Infancy, (2) Muhammad Becomes an Orphan, (3) Muhammad in Mecca in Care of an Uncle, (4) Muhammad's (pbuh) Youth, (5) Muhammad Acts as Caravan Agent for Wealthy Tradesw, (6) Muhammad's (saw) Marriage and Family Life, (7) Muhammad(saw) Receives First Revelation, (8) Muhammad(saw) Takes his Message Public, (9) Muhammad(saw) and the Muslims Emigrate to Medina, (10) The Military Period, (11) The Conquest of Mecca, and (12) Muhammad's(saw) Final Years. The timeline is interactive, with options for 'Arabic', 'AH', 'Zoom Out', 'Zoom In', and 'Zoom Reset'. A 'Rotate Speed: 10 Secs' slider is also visible at the bottom.

Fig. 8 A time-line showing events during Prophet (saw) life time

etc., information about rulers, battles and other events. The application contains information in English/Arabic, Timelines, Maps, Images and much more. Fig. 8 shows a time-line showing events during Prophet (saw) life time (<http://history.muslimscholars.info>).

V. CONCLUSION

Some interactive and beneficial/Islamic web applications are presented. The details of features, benefits, resources used, and implementation are also discussed. This is believed to be the first extensive work related to online Islamic knowledge in

English. These applications can benefit general public as well as student of Islamic knowledge. It also provides information which was never available in any other language except Arabic, however, this site is quite useful for Arabic speaking Muslim as information is also available in Arabic. This work can be extended to have other collection of Islamic knowledge. We can also use state of the art data mining techniques to correlate between different Islamic sciences like ahadeeth can be matched in terms of subject matter with corresponding Qur'anic verses.

REFERENCES

- [1] Ibn Ishaq, Ibn Hisham (trans:A. Guillaume, *The Life O f Muhammad (SAW), Sirat Radul Allah*, Oxford University Press, 1955(2003 16th Impression) (originally written around 800 CE).
- [2] Ibn Sad, *Tabaqat Ibn Sa'd (Urdu Trans. Vol 2,3, 4)*, Karachi, Pakistan: Darul Ishaq, 2003 (originally written around 825 CE).
- [3] Ibn Hibban, *at-Thaqat*, Online Arabic Resource, originally written around 850 CE.
- [4] Muhammad Ibn Ismail alBukhari, *al-Tarikh-ul-Kabir*, Online Arabic Resource, originally written around 850 CE.
- [5] Muhammad bin Jarir al-Tabari, *The History of al-Tabari (vol. XXXIX) - Biographies of the Prophet's Companions/Successor*, New York, USA: SUNY Press, 1998 (originally written around 900 CE).
- [6] Muhammad ibn Ahmed ibn 'Usman al-Dhahbi, *Siyar A'lam al-Nubala*, Online Arabic Resource, originally written around 1325 CE.
- [7] Ibn Hajar, *al-Isabah*, Online Arabic Resource, originally written around 1430 CE.
- [8] Yusuf ibn 'Abd al-Rahman al-Mizzi, *Tahdheeb al-Kamal*, Online Arabic Resource, originally written around 1325 CE.
- [9] 'Abdul Ghani Al-Maqdisi, *Short Biography of The Prophet (saw) and His Ten Companions (trans.)*, Riyadh, KSA: DarusSalam, 2004.
- [10] Mahmood A. Gadanfar, *Great Women of Islam*, Riyadh, KSA: DarusSalam, 2001.
- [11] Research Division (trans:Sameh Strach), *Child Companions around the Prophet(pbuh)*, Riyadh, KSA: DarusSalam, 2003.

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